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Improving Vocabulary Skills Using Video Games

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***Abstract:** In learning a foreign language, vocabulary plays an important role. It is the element which links the four skills of language learning, for example speaking, listening, reading and writing all together. In order to communicate well in a foreign language, students should acquire an adequate number of words and should know how to use them accurately. Therefore, the present article has reviewed the effects of using video games on improving vocabulary learning in an English as foreign language or English as second language context. Different studies revealed that games are beneficial in vocabulary learning because they enhance students' ability to memorize words, encourage student's interaction, improve their communicative skills and enhance students' motivation. Games also can help the teachers to create contexts in which the language is useful and meaningful. This study aimed to guide teachers and students towards a better understanding of vocabularies through educational games.*

***Key words:** video games, educational game, vocabulary, motivation, meaningful context.*

Children's access to media devices has dramatically increased within a short time period. A recent report on children, age 8 and under in the United States, found a vefold increase to tablets and more than 20% increase to both smartphones and mobile devices from 2011 to 2013. The number of children who used a mobile device doubled while the number of minutes spent on the device tripled.

As a result, the American Academy of Pediatrics raised concern about the possible harmful effects and suggested the duration of time children spend with mobile media could be potentially problematic. Earlier recommendations on electronic media use were somewhat vague, but included time-based guidelines and encouraged parents to establish a home use plan. Just recently, the AAP relaxed their recommendations and sug-gested that positive effects from mobile media could aid children. New technologies are often rightly a source of concern, but in this case, some of the concerns stem from the dearth of research on the validity, or even usability of these types of devices for children. These new media platforms have led to a rise in new media forms; applications, or apps, are a key part of the

experience users have with mobile devices. Common Sense Media found that children, age 8 and under, who used apps increased from 16% in 2011 to 50% in 2013.

The array of mobile devices and significant increase in use along with the explosion of apps affords opportunities to use these as tools to impact educational outcomes and facilitate learning during development. This potential has not yet been realized. Games are an important subset of apps, and learning games have a long history. Our view is that games, when designed appropriately, can facilitate meaningful learning experiences. In this paper, we explicitly speak to educational games on mobile platforms, although many of these principles could have broader use in more general application development. We present five principles driven from empirical findings in child development and connect them to an educational game.

That is, we argue educational games should: have developmentally appropriate content; integrate the theoretical frameworks from learning sciences; embed learning in socially rich contexts; develop diverse content; and create a balance between play and real-world learning opportunities. There is an existing literature that provides guidelines on the development and design of educational games [5, 15].

This article provides the foundation to understand how design features in children's media plays an important role. While many reference other kinds of media such as television and computer systems, some of the principles in our paper overlap with previous work. Our framework differs in three important ways. First, our goal is to provide a framework that directly speaks to interactive media devices such as tablets and smartphones. Second, we strive to incorporate research principles from developmental science to inform game development. Third, we provide guidance on how to select educational content for a certain population, 2–3 year olds, to learn language. Throughout the paper, we draw on a hypothetical game, one that is designed to be played on a mobile device as an educational game for 2–3-year-old children with the goal to facilitate language learning and development. Our example is derived from our own research program that seeks to create innovative and meaningful educational experiences to facilitate language development in 2–3-year-old children from low-income communities. Our imagined game is fundamentally an interactive story because studies have demonstrated that book reading interventions, and especially those where the child is an active participant, can significantly increase language skills.

The role of games in teaching and learning vocabulary cannot be denied. However, in order to achieve the most from vocabulary games, it is essential that suitable games be chosen. Whenever a game is to be used, the proficiency level and cultural background of the students should be taken into account, and also it should be useful for students with lower language ability and should be easily applied in the class. Many experienced textbook and methodological manual writers have argued that games are not just time-filling activities but have a great educational value.

This article offers the rationale for implementing games as a stress-free tool of learning words. It is believed that games can have the potentiality to contextualize learning words. DeHaan, Reed and Kuwada investigated the effect of interactivity with a music video game on second language vocabulary recall. The participants of their study were divided into two groups; one of them played an English-language music video game for 20 minutes, while the other group watched the game simultaneously on another monitor. After playing the game, a vocabulary recall test, an experience questionnaire, and a two week delayed vocabulary recall test were administered. The results of their study showed that both the players and the watchers of the video game recalled vocabulary from the game, but the players recalled less vocabulary than the watchers. DeHaan argued that although a video game that contains target language vocabulary can be enjoyable, its interactivity can prevent language

acquisition process because of this players were unable to recall the game's vocabulary as well as watchers. They also argued that "players of the video game were asked to play the game and attend to the vocabulary simultaneously and these multiple foci of attention prevented them from noticing and recalling more vocabulary items than the watchers" [5, 85.].

Video games is interactive, which at the same time is suitable for 21st century learner who are craving for technologies. Thus, this study was conducted. Data collection was done in a primary school in South of Malaysia which two class being sampled. The two classrooms were separated into control group and experimental group. Before any statistical test being conducted, the data was tested for its normality. For this research, the researchers had performed Shapiro-Wilk test. Based on the test, the data was found as normally distributed. To study the effectiveness of video games in facilitating ESL classroom, a Paired Sample T-Test was conducted to measure the different between the pretest and posttest score. A significant different was visible from the test. Further statistical test shows that experimental group perform better that their counterpart in control group.

The paired sample t-test is being conducted and the result shown that there is a significant the pretest and posttest of the experimental group. This indicating that the treatment is giving positive impact toward the samples. convince that video games might be ideal in preparing workers for today's workplace that traditional one. Yet, what is importance is the capability of video games to allow the re-creation of user in new world and achieve deep learning at the same time. The question either video game is effective in enhancing sample's vocabulary was answered by the t-test conducted as stated above. It can be concluded that video games is actually an effective tool in enhancing ESL vocabulary as suggested by Gee that a well-designed video game has a higher probability of delivering outcomes because of its ability to enhance theoretical or contemporary pedagogy which will lead towards success in learning. In normal classroom, memorization create a wall for students to develop their higher order thinking skill. It is contradicting the practice of modern education. As what being proposed by in order to develop high level thinking, student need to engage complex and meaningful projects that demand collaboration, research, management of resources, and the development of an ambitious performance or product.

As hammer states 'If language structure makes up the skeleton of language, then it is vocabulary that provides the vital organs and flesh'. It is one element that links the four skills of speaking, listening, reading and writing all together. In order to communicate well in a foreign language, students should acquire an adequate number of words and should know how to use them accurately. In conclusion, organizing and teaching vocabularies through various videos and games is a very effective way. therefore, I think such techniques should be applied more to students.

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